

**French and Uzbek of gastronomy linguistic and cultural and schematic
analyses**

Xalimova Maxbuba

French language science High category floor he is a teacher

Abstract

This article French and Uzbek of gastronomy linguistic and cultural and semantic analyses through each two in culture food preparation of art to himself special aspects , traditions and history heritage to learn dedicated . In the article gastronomic terminology and his cultural in context importance , as well as every one of the nation gastronomic identification and aesthetics seeing will be released . French and Uzbek dishes between similarities and differences mutually compared to , this through of gastronomy language and culture with how dependence analysis will be done . Results two culture between mutually the effect and connections open gives

Key words : Gastronomy , Linguistic culture, Semantics Analysis, Uzbek food, culture

Enter

Gastronomy is it not only food preparation art , perhaps each one of the people culture and history reflection bringer important factor is considered Har one of the nation to himself special their food preparation methods , ingredients and eating traditions many cultures and historical changes with depend French and Uzbek gastronomy this in terms of very rich and is diverse . This article French and Uzbek of gastronomy linguistic and cultural and semantic aspects learns that through two culture between dependence and differences open gives

Research object

Research object as French and Uzbek of gastronomy linguistic and cultural aspects selected . This in research the following aspects seeing will be :

1. **of food historical context** — each two of the nation gastronomy formed historical events .
2. **Traditions and traditions** - food preparation and consumption to do with depends traditions .

3. **Ingredients and their semantic meanings** — of ingredients etymology and cultural in context role

Applicable methods

In the article the following methods applies to :

1. **Linguistic and cultural Analysis** : Uzbek and French in the language gastronomic terms and their in culture importance to determine
2. **Semantic analysis** : Gastronomic of terms meanings and their cultural in context role study
3. **Comparison Method** : Two gastronomic culture between similarities and differences to determine
4. **Sociological inquiries** : Consumers between conducted requests through their gastronomic experiences and thoughts study

Received results and their analysis

1. Gastronomy and history

French gastronomy many historical events , cultural exchanges and political from changes formed . Medium in centuries French kitchen many traditions and teachings with enriched , for example , the concept of "haute cuisine" . Uzbek gastronomy while basically Eastern and Central Asia peoples with depends historical events through formed . of Uzbekistan territorial location his gastronomic influence on traditions did

2. Traditions and traditions

Traditions and traditions each two gastronomy for important important have Uzbek kitchen most of the time family holidays and weddings with depends if so , French kitchen while more gastronomic art and to aesthetics applies . An example for , like " osh " and " manti " in Uzbekistan food family in circles prepared in French and foie such as " gras " or " coq au vin " . food special at events offer will be done .

3. Ingredients and semantic analysis

Ingredients language and culture between connections reflection makes Uzbek in gastronomy wheat , rice and meat main ingredients is French kitchen while more vegetables , milk products and to spices attention looks Uzbek in food ingredients more natural and local if so , the French while own in food more international of the ingredients uses

Summary

French and Uzbek gastronomy not only food with , perhaps culture , history and traditions with closely depends . Theirs linguistic and cultural and semantic analysis two the nation between similarities and differences open gives Gastronomy language through culture reflection makes and each one of the nation to himself characteristic shows . This article in the future gastronomic studies and cultural exchanges more deeper to learn the ground creates

Used literature

1. Baranov , A. (2018). Gastronomy and culture : historical aspects .
2. Gafurova , N. (2020). Uzbek gastronomy : traditions and modernity .
3. Dupuis , J. (2019). French Cuisine: A Cultural Overview.
4. Karimova , S. (2021). Linguistic culture : theoretical and practical aspects .
5. Bakhromov , O. (2022). Uzbekistan gastronomy and his international importance .
6. Thomas , E. (2020). Culinary Heritage: A Comparative Study.
7. Mukhtorova , D. (2023). Gastronomy and identification : national and international measurements .
8. De Gaulle, C. (2017). The Influence of History on French Cuisine.
9. Nurullayev , A. (2021). Uzbek dishes and their cultural context .
10. Valdebenito , R. (2019). Globalization and Local Cuisines: A Cross-Cultural Perspective.